

STANCE TAKING IN THE SERMON, “THE POWER OF DEDICATION”

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Abstract

Bishop Adhlakun’s messages are sites for posturing Christianity in Nigeria and the need to live a pleasing life to God. Existing linguistic and nonlinguistic studies on religious discourses, especially from the Christendom focused mostly on clergymen like Pastor Enoch Adeboye, Bishop Oyedepo, Pastor Paul Eneche and others, with little attention paid to the stances in the message of Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun. Therefore, this study was designed to examine language use in Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun sermon. This was with a view to determining the stances taken and the engagement markers employed. Ken Hyland’s Stance and Engagement Theory, served as the framework. The descriptive design was adopted. Bishop Taiwo Victor’s message “The Power of Dedication was purposively selected. The broadcasts were downloaded from YouTube. The data were subjected to discourse analysis. The dominant stances taken are dedication is the only way to distinction, most Christians are not living dedicated purposeful life, the only ways to be dedicated are through focus and concentration and total dedication is evident in one’s work with God All the nine engagement markers (hedges, boosters, attitude markers, self-mention, reader/listener pronouns, directives, questions, shared knowledge and personal asides) were used by Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun. The study concludes that Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun’s speeches on the “The Power of dedication” is imbued with various stances. The study also recommends that research should be conducted on the pragmatic acts in the message.

Keywords: Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun, Dedication, Religious Discourse, Stance Taking

Introduction

Language and religion cannot be separated as it is through language that the doctrines and dogmas of religion are expressed (Okpeh and Nnamele, 2023). Both of them are part of human existence, as they are portrayals of the human existence. They are one of the features that separate us from other animals (Okpeh and David, 2020). Saraswathi (2020, p. 7) believes that there is no way one can understand a religion without first understanding the language that is associated to it. For instance, Christianity is so much attached to English, although, Catholicism attached so much emphasis on Latin, Islamic is Arabic; Judaism makes use of Hebrews, Theravada Buddhists use Pali and so, the case with other religions. Moreover, most of these

religions have attachment to particular region or the other. For instance, Islamic is believed to have strength in the continent of Asia and some parts of Africa, while Christianity predominately occupies the continents of Europe, Southern and Northern and America, Australia and other parts of Africa as well.

In the case of Nigeria, there are three predominant religions: Islam, Christianity and African Traditional Religions (Ngbea, 2018; Onipede and Edun, 2021; Mudashir and Mubarak, 2025). And this religious aspect of Nigeria has always shown itself not only in the socio-political activities of the Nigerian people, but in all other aspects of the country. It can be said that the religious sector has really blended with the lifestyles of Nigerians, which has become part and parcel of them. This has also given the country a recognition as one of the most religious nations on the globe. Currently, it is a secular state that allows freedom of religion as enshrined in her 1999 Constitution (Ngbea, 2018). Moreover, the speeches of their clergymen from the three major religions have been given scholarly attention from sociology, political science, peace and conflict, linguistics and others. The sermons of those clergymen from all religions have been scholarly examined to be characterized with lots of rhetorics demonstrated through some linguistic nuances (Ngbea, 2018; Okpeh and David, 2020).

The concern of this current study is not rhetorics but on stances. Stance has been summarized by Ugah (2019), looking at the works of Du Bois (2007), as a socially constructive and dynamic phenomenon, relational and psychological, socially and culturally bound, epistemic, interactional and expressive through intensifiers. Also, Du Bois (2007) opines that stance taking is the evaluation of entities in the discourse by a speaker (subject). It is the judgement a speaker or writer sometimes deduces from an interaction. It is judgement taken by a speaker toward object, people, idea, concept and so on (Iwasaki and Ha Yap, 2015). Here, stance taking has been defined as an intersubjective activity in which co-participants display their stances by simultaneously using the multitude of linguistic resources available to them and by deploying the sequential aspects of interaction and turn design (Haddington, 2004).

Studies (Oguntola-Laguda, 2015; Ibezim, 2017; Ngbea, 2018; Abar, 2019; Okpeh and David, 2020; Onipede and Edun, 2021; Oluremi, 2021; Okpeh and Nnamele, 2023) Mudashir and Mubarak, 2025) and others have investigated religions in Nigeria and their influences on the socio-political and economic nature of Nigeria, and the rhetorics that characterized the sermons of their clergymen from Islamic and Christian viewpoints. Some of the studies on the Christian clergymen concentrated on Adeboye, Enenche, Oyedapo, Kumiyi and others, with little attention given to Bishop Taiwo Victor Adedokun's sermons. This is the central focus of this

current study, with the view of determining the stances that are embedded in his sermons, and how the engagement tools in Hyland (2005) helped in taking those stances. This study would contribute but greatly to studies on stances, religious discourse and linguistics entirely.

Brief Note on Bishop Taiwo Victor Adedokun

Bishop Taiwo Victor Adedokun is the Chancellor of Dominion University, Ibadan. Nigeria. Born on 26th May, 1963, he hails from Oyo State, Nigeria. Attended Methodist Primary School, Ekotedo, Ibadan; Baptist High School, Iwo, 1975-1980; Federal Government College, Odogbolu, 1980-82, University of Lagos, 1982-86. An estate surveyor turned Pastor, he is the General Overseer and Presiding Bishop of Victory International Church (Rehoboth Cathedral), with branches within and outside Nigeria. He has authored the following books: *Tithing-Key to Prosperity*; *Risk for Returns*; *Kingdom Benefits*; *Demonic Dreams and Integrity: Path to Prosperity*. All published by Victory Publishing house. Bishop Adedokun married Pastor Mrs. Oludolapo Adedokun in 1991 and the marriage is blessed with two children: David and Joshua.

Literature review

Okpe and David (2020) studied the pragmatic import of rhetorical devices in the messages of Christian clerics using the sermon of Pastor Paul Eneche, the Senior Pastor of the Dunamis International Gospel Centre. The data for the study were elicited from two of his sermons. The sermons were transcribed for the purpose of identifying the rhetorical devices contained therein. P. H. Grice's (1975) Cooperative Principle served as the theoretical mirror to which help in determining the rhetorical devices that are prevalent in his sermons, especially how the cooperative maxims were flouted. From the result, it was revealed that the best linguistic resources deployed by Pentecostal ministers are rhetorical devices in order to make their messages impactful, memorable and persuasive. It was also discovered that those devices help clergymen to heighten the emotions of their congregation and also to increase participation.

Investigating linguistic elements among white garment ministers, Onipede and Edun (2021) did an analysis of the generic structure and the pragmatic imports in Reverend EMF Oshoffa's sermons. He chosen to represent other ministers owing to his large audience. thirty-two (32) excerpts selected from Reverend EMF Oshoffa's sermons through participants and non-participant observations. The findings revealed the GSP catalogue for Reverend EMF Oshoffa as $[P]^{\wedge} [S]^{\wedge} (DoP)^{\wedge} [Se]^{\wedge} \{(CfC)^{\wedge} (WtF)\}^{\wedge} [F]$. Elements generated in the catalogue include: prayer P, Song S, Greeting G, Declaration of Purpose DoP, Sermon Se, Call for Confession CfC, Welcome to the Fold WtF, and Finis F. While DoP, CfC and WtF are optional, the

remaining ones (P, S, G, Se and F) are obligatory. The findings revealed that most registers used in patterning CCC sermons feature 'angelic registers' whose meanings cannot be traced to any world languages, but their meanings can be inferred from the context of use. Notable registers of the sermon featured El-beraca-bered-Eli, Elmorijah, Elohimjah, and Eli-Bamah-Yabah. The paper concluded that the elements of GSP catalogued here are typical of CCC sermonic discourse.

Okpeh and Nnamele (2023) combined pragmatic and discourse analysis viewpoints to analyse the selected sermons of Pastor Adeboye. Ten of his sermons during Holy Ghost Services served as the data. These were selected from his official YouTube preached between 2010 –2012. The sermons were transcribed and subjected to analysis using a triangulation of insights from Mey's (2001a) Pragmatic Acts Theory, Korta and Perry's (2011) Critical Pragmatic Theory, and Gee's (2005) Notion of Discourse. The findings of the study revealed three pragmatic practs associated with Adeboye's sermons: assuring, threatening, and prophesying. The practs were realised through shared situation knowledge (SSK), voice (VCE) and reference (REF). Also, it proved that words can be used as instrument of saying, doing things and enacting varying identities.

Oluremi (2021) examined the discursive structure of waka chants as performed by Islamic clerics among the Yoruba Muslims at the event of *fidā'u*. Eight documented *Waka* chants in honour of some deceased Muslims in South-western Nigeria were sampled. The waka chants which were mainly in the Yoruba language as rendered by Muslim clerics were transcribed and translated to English language for the purpose of analysis. Mey's theory of pragmeme served as the theoretical conceptual, the paper ascertained that waka chants at the event of *fidā'u* possess inherent pragmatic forces beyond their invocation to elucidate sermons and lives of a deceased Muslim. Such chants, this paper argues, perform socio-religious actions which are of immense benefits to the living.

In addition to religious discourses from Islamic viewpoint, Mudashir and Mubarak (2025) investigated the use of some anti-Islamic expression among Yoruba Muslim. Some states predominately occupied by Yoruba Muslims were used as the sample population. Dell Hymes' (1974) *Ethnography of SPEAKING* served as theoretical perspective, while the Yoruba data were interpreted using Baker's (2018) 'textual' and 'pragmatic' equivalence approach. The result revealed that educated Yoruba-Muslims use the expressions mostly as shown in the 49 (61.25%) respondents educational environments against 31 (38.75%) from domestic localities. Based on gender, 45 male respondents representing 56.25% and 35 female respondents

representing 43.75% proof their difference. It is recommended that linguistic researches should be carried out on anti-Christian expressions in order to afford for sanctity of the society through the power of language without fear or favour of one religion over another. Although Okpe and David (2020), Onipede and Edun (2021) and Okpeh and Nnamele (2023) are connected to Christian religious discourse, this current study it is neither on white garment, Pastor Adeboye nor on generic structure, but on the message of Bishop Adedokun, focusing on his stances on dedication.

Theoretical insight

This study adopted Ken Hyland's Stance and Engagement Theory. It was propounded in 2005. Both stance and engagement are taken to be two sides of a coin, as through them writers present themselves, their works and show solidarity with their readers (Hyland, 2005). Stance stands for writer-oriented features in interaction and the ways writers' comment on the accuracy of a claim, the extent they show their commitment to it or the attitude they want to express to a proposition or the reader (Hyland, 2005). Furthermore, Hyland also asserted that the marking of stance and engagement is also context bound. According to Hyland (2005:7), stance concerns *writer-oriented features* of interaction and refers to the ways academics annotate their texts to comment on the possible accuracy or credibility of a claim, the extent they want to commit themselves to it, or the attitude they want to convey to an entity, a proposition, or the reader. Stance is sub-divided into: hedges which helps writer or speakers bring in other people's opinion to reduce their total commitment to a proposition. They include linguistic terms such as possible, perhaps, might and so on.

Boosters show certainty towards a proposition and they include devices such as *clearly, obviously, surely*, etc. and modal verbs like *will, must, can*, and the like (Moini and Salami, 2015). Attitude markers express the writer's opinion toward propositions that convey surprise, frustration, importance, agreement, and so on. They are conveyed through verbs like *agree* and *prefer*; sentence adverbs such as *unfortunately* and *hopefully*; and adjectives such as *appropriate, logical* and *remarkable*. Other ways by which attitude markers are indicated in discourses are punctuation, subordination, comparative, progressive particles. Self-mention helps to consciously give the explicit presence or absence of writers in order to take a specific stance and identification of authority (Hyland, 2005). It is measured by the use of first-person pronouns "I", "we", "me", "us", "mine", "ours" and possessive adjectives "my", "our" to explicitly show the writer's presence in the text (Hyland, 2005).

Engagement on the other side of the coin is an alignment dimension where writers acknowledge and connect to their readers or listeners, recognizing their presence; carrying them along with their argument; focusing on their attention; acknowledging their uncertainties; including them as participants and guiding them to the interpretation of whatsoever is being discussed (Hyland, 2005:177). It includes reader pronouns realized through the second-person pronoun “you” and the possessive adjective “your”; personal asides allow writers to involve readers in a stream of discourse by interrupting the argument briefly just to offer a comment on what has been said; through directives, discourse participants are instructed to do or view something in the course of the discourse in accordance with the way the writer determines it. These are achieved via consider, note, and imagine); modals of obligation (must, should, and ought) and through a predicative adjective like “it is important to understand”.

Hyland (2002) divided directives into three subgroups, namely, textual, physical and cognitive directives. Shared Knowledge helps writer/speaker to share ideas that his or her readers are aware of; while questions are used by writers/speakers to arouse interest and curiosity of the readers over an argument (Moini and Salami, 2015). So, the adoption of this theory becomes imperative as it would help the study in identifying the stances that are embedded in Bishop Taiwo Victor Adedokun’s sermon and outline the engagement markers deployed.

The chart below shows the division of stance and engagement elements by Hyland (2005).

Figure 2.1: A chart showing stance and engagement features.

Source: Hyland, K. 2005. Stance and engagement: a model of interaction in academic discourse. *Discourse Studies* 7.2:175-192.

Data and Analytical Procedure

This study adopts a qualitative research design. The actions, reactions, events, attitude and linguistic choices and the prevailing context in Bishop Adelaku's Message, *The Power of Dedication*. His message marked a period where consistency and persistency in Christianity, especially total dedication to God has been a challenge. Through the qualitative analysis, the message was divided into extracts with dominant stances in them. Engagement markers deployed in each extract are emboldened. The data were subjected to discourse analyses.

Data presentation and analysis

This segment focuses on the analysis and discussion of findings of the study. The analysis follows a top-down approach. The dominant stances adopted by Bishop Taiwo Victor Adalakun are presented. Words, phrases and clauses in excerpts elicited for the analysis serving as pointers to engagement markers are emboldened.

Dedication is the only way to Distinction

Through the deployment of various engagement markers, Bishop Adalakun takes his stance on the importance of dedication. He sees dedication as the only way one can achieve distinction. This is demonstrated through the excerpt below:

Excerpt 1: The power of dedication. **Ever seen power of dedication? Say louder. If you can** get this message right, **you will** be enjoying the life of distinction **without** stress. The power of dedication. Because **until you** sort the issue of dedication out, **there is no question of distinction. You can never** become a distinguished fellow **until you** have sorted the issue of dedication out (Bishop T.V Adalakun's message on "The Power of Dedication").

The first tool deployed by Bishop Adalakun to take his stance on dedication is question. According to Hyland (2005), question is a strong dialogical tool used by speaker/writer to involve their participants in a stream of discourse. This is also similar to the use of reader pronouns. Both are deployed to carry the listeners along and for them to understand the importance of a dedicated Christian living and to ignite the interest of the listeners on his stance. The use of "ever" at the beginning of the question is a strong booster element to show the certainty of the proposition he was about to take. "Say louder" shows attitude to what the stance is on dedication, and also an element of inclusion in the stream of discourse. It also

marks importance as an attitude marker in the message. Moreover, it is an element of directive, where the listeners are asked to carry out an action, for the purpose of digestion and absorption of his proposition.

He used “readers pronoun” often to arouse the interest of his listeners. Boosters: *without, can never, until* and *will* are all deployed to show the certainty in his stance that distinction will never be achieved if there is no dedication. Both of them are repeatedly used to show emphasis in the stance Bishop Adelakun takes on the importance of dedication and to show his positive attitude towards a dedicated life as a means of success and his negative attitude to a life that is not dedicated. His attitude also shows the certainty that a life that is not dedicated will only end in failure.

Excerpt 2: To be dedicated means **you** are separated to thy cause. **You** are set apart. **That's what it means.** When a verse is dedicated, or a people are dedicated, **you** don't live for everything, **you** live for something (Bishop T.V Adelakun’s message on “The Power of Dedication”).

Reader pronoun is used to reiterate his stance on dedication being a sure way to distinction. He used that in the excerpt above to still arouse the interest of the listener by making know that why they need to be dedicated is because they are distinct. This is further demonstrated through the contrast he utilized “everything” and “something. The something marks importance of being dedicated as one has been created for a spectacular goal in life, excellence.

Excerpt 3: **Let's** look at **Paul**, look at **Jesus**, and look at a **few people in the Bible, people that live dedicated lives. And make up your mind** that **you** are going to live a life of dedication **because that's where the power for distinction lies.** Galatians 1, verse 15. Romans 11, verse 13. **Can we** read that? **Can we** read it now? (Bishop T.V Adelakun’s message on “The Power of Dedication”).

In excerpt 3, he used self-mention “let’s” and “we” to show solidarity with others on his stance. They all help to consciously give the explicit presence of Bishop Adelakun and his congregation in order to take a stance on dedication being the sure way to distinction. It also stamped his authority. The use of question helped to involve the congregation in the topic of discussion. The questions are also directives asking the congregation to carry out a task, reading from the Bible to read about entities that were dedicated in the Bible. The attitude of Bishop Adelakun towards the Jesus, Paul and the Bible is positive.

This is to mark the importance of dedication in the Christian living as they are presented as the models for Christians who desire to be distinct. He presented Jesus and others who attempted distinction through their dedicated lifestyle. He used the structure “because that's where the power for distinction lies” to emphasize the importance of a dedicated lifestyle. So, from the above, Bishop Adalaku confidently took his stance that the only way to attempt distinctive level in life is to be dedicated.

Most Christians are not living dedicated purposeful life

Instances of the stance of Bishop Adalaku on Christians not living dedicated purposeful life are given in some excerpts below:

Excerpt 4: There are many Christians today, they don't know exactly why they are in this world and what they are supposed to do. They **just** live their Christian life day in day out **without** finding a purpose. **Just** go to church, trust what you are supposed to do to be good. **What are you specifically called to do? I** remember a young man who came to me and said, Sir, I'm a stammerer and I know that I cannot preach, **but** I have so many ideas that have been translated into resources. **And God told me; I** am here to support the **work of God** in **your** hands. **That's the purpose.** Another man came to **me.** He was trying to speak in **English.** **So, I** saw he was struggling. **I** said, okay. This kind of money in his hand. He said, **I** have discovered **my** purpose. **My** purpose is to make life easy for **you.** **No other thing** (Bishop T.V Adalaku's message on “The Power of Dedication”).

The first element used in introducing Bishop Adalaku's stance on most Christians are not living dedicated purposeful life is shared background knowledge. Both the speaker and the listeners understand the fact that they are some Christians are that struggling in identifying their purpose in life, and truly need to be helped. The involvement of the above discussion also project hedges as it helps in bringing in other people's opinion that truly most Christians are not living a dedicated purposeful life which affects their efficiency in ministry and life generally. And his attitude towards that is negative. The use of “just” and “without” help to show his certainty in his stance that he is sure of his stance. He used self-mention “I and “me” to stamp his authoritative presence as one who has experience and counted himself different from those people, he takes stance against. Also, engaging the conversation of those young men who visited him to talk about their purposes in life served as form hedges to concretize his argument that most Christians are not living a dedicated Christian life, while others do. The question asked specially meant to ignite the curiosity of his listeners in agreeing with his proposition.

His attitude towards the level of English of and understanding of the men in the quoted speech is negative. He sees them as not having purpose in life. While his attitude towards God is positive, he believes that God is the one who ordains men to be purposeful in life. But the inclusion of God in the man's defense to show that God directed him to contribute to Bishop Adalakun's ministry seem satirical, as it can be inferred that the men did not understand what their purposes in life are. The last segment of the excerpt is a booster which shows the certainty Bishop Adalakun holds that the last man in the quoted speech do not have any purpose in life. That is, nothing reasonable to

Excerpt 5: There are some of us who don't know the purpose for which we are in the body of Christ. We are just doing competition with other people all over the place. You must find out what is the purpose of God and the plans of God for your life and be true to it. Someone else are around, they are finding it, but you have not found it, you have been here for years. You can't be dedicated to a course you don't know, and you will never know until you seek to find out, why am I here? What purpose? Or what purpose am I in this place? Let's look at Jesus, John chapter 18, verse 37. Heard what Jesus said in that passage. John 18 verse 37. "Pilate therefore said to him, are you the king then? Jesus answered, thou said I'm a king. And to this end was I born. King of kings and Lord of lords. And for this cause came I into the world, that I should be a witness unto the truth. Everyone that is of the truth, they heareth my voice." Clear purpose! He was dedicated to clear purpose, clean purpose (Bishop T.V Adalakun's message on "The Power of Dedication").

He used hedges to include other people's opinion and also self-mention prove that Bishop Adalakun is not exempting himself from those who lack purpose in life. This could be a technique deployed to show solidarity with others who have not been able to live a dedicated purposeful Christian life that there is hope, and must understand that that is what the body of Christ needs. The involvement of the body of Christ in the above excerpt is a testament of the positive attitude that Bishop Adalakun holds on the importance of having members who are dedicated purposefully. And it also shows the high regards he has for the Christendom.

God has been presented as the supreme being who ordains all human to be purposeful in life. And through this, it can be deduced in the excerpt above that total dedication to God is what will make one to be purposeful in life according to the stance that he takes. In addition, the use of the coordinating conjunction in the above marks the use of booster, where Bishop Adalakun believes as long others are realizing their purpose in life, his listeners are not exceptional to that. Furthermore, he uses question to arouse their interest in the discourse by making them to fully participate in the interaction, where at the end will correct their perception on living without a dedicated purpose in life, especially as Christians.

The story of Jesus and Pilate in the Bible is not new to his listeners. Through shared background knowledge, they know what transpired between Jesus and Pilate when He (Jesus) was taken to him (Pilate) for questioning before sentenced dead. Bishop Adalakun used that to show his attitude towards Jesus as the model any Christian who desires to live a dedicated purposeful life. He sees the response given to Pilate by Jesus as a clear-cut purpose, as Jesus was not deterred with the challenge before Him but stood for the purpose which God has dedicated Him for. The quotation of the scripture showing the conversation between Jesus and Pilate is a form of hedges in order to bring in what the Bible talks about purpose and not from the speaker's opinion. This is according to Hyland (2005), where hedges are seen as elements which help writer or speakers bring in other people's opinion to reduce their total commitment to a proposition. So, the quotation of the Bible has reduced Bishop Adalakun's total commitment to the proposition that it is important to live a dedicated purposeful life as Christians.

The only ways to be dedicated are through focus and concentration

Explanations of the above stance are given in the excerpts below, and this is done through the various engagement markers available in Hyland's (2005) Stance and Engagement Theory:

Excerpt 6: Because of time, let's look at how can a person be dedicated. **You** know there are those who are doing high service. **If your** service is from the heart, **you** have a reward from hell. **If your** service **God does not recognize it. What makes for dedication? Focus and concentration. How do you identify those who are dedicated in church?** Their focus and their concentration on the assignment. **That's the proof of dedication. That's the proof of dedication.** When you are not playing games with **God**, you are not involved in negotiating, you take **God** plainly and act on it. That's dedication. **Focus, concentration, focus, concentration.** Because there are many things that distract us. Until you take care of them, you can never be dedicated. One of the things you need to take care of is your flesh. That's one major thing you need to tame. Because the flesh does not want to do the will of God. The flesh is looking for an easy way out. **And dedication comes at a price! It's not cheap! Focus and concentration!** I'm going to show you this now. When we talk, we are looking at Paul as an example. **Let's look at Focus and concentration of Paul. In Philippians chapter 3 verse 13, verse 13 and 14 rather, hear what the Bible says there. It says, I count not myself to have apprehended, but this one thing I do This is a statement of focus and concentration.** This one thing I do, forgetting those things which lie behind and reaching forth onto those things which are before. And then he went on to say, consecrate upon that I press. I press towards the mark of the icon of God (Bishop T.V Adalakun's message on "The Power of Dedication").

Bishop Adalakun used directive to ask his listeners to verify where instances of the major ways to dedication are illustrated in the Bible. He used self-mention to show solidarity with his listeners as being part of the teaching process. The references given to God and the Bible

are evidences of his positive attitude towards them, and to prove their credibility, not by bringing his own opinion but other higher authorities (God and the Bible) through the deployment of hedges. These help him to show that the subject of dedication was not his product but God's ordinance for man in order to achieve purpose in life. He used "I" as a self-mention to stamp his authority in the subject, focus and concentration as the ways to total dedication. Also, repetition of certain structures "Focus and concentration" and "proof of dedication" are boosters which show certainty in Bishop Adelakun's proposition

In addition, questions are there to arouse the interest and attention of the congregation, and to some extent to mark of importance of focus and concentration as the ways of being dedicated. So, from the above except and explanation, Bishop Adelakun has critically taken his stance that focus and concentration are the best ways to prove one's dedication.

Total Dedication is evident in one's work with God

The confidence that Bishop Adelakun has on God has made him to take his stance that total dedication to Him, God, is evident in one's work with God. That is, one cannot say he or she is dedicated to God and is not working with God. This is typically exemplified in excerpt 7 below:

Excerpt 7: And you know, when it comes to working with God, if you work with God for some while, you'll find that He has His processes. **If you If you** lose concentration, you go to the back and start all over again. Because part of the thing that marks us is our consistency. C.S. Diamond, as he is diligent in his business, he **will** stand before kings. **You will never** find him among may men or riffraff. When you see a dedicated soul, he **will** be rated with the highest of the highest. When you see a man that's not dedicated, he **will** be among the lowest of the lowest because there's no focus, there's no concentration. I press, this one thing I do, I press, this one thing I do (Bishop T.V Adelakun's message on "The Power of Dedication").

The speaker, Bishop Adelakun believes that when one is dedicated to God, it is evidence-based. Everyone will see it deployed the use of reader pronoun to include his congregation as he takes his stance that dedicated lifestyle is evident when works with God. He uses hedges to bring in C.S. Diamond's assertion on how the evidence of one working with God is: not standing among may men or riffraff, rated with the highest, while the man who is dedicated can be identified with men of lowest level in the society. This application has helped him reduced his assertion or proposition that total dedication is evident in one's work with God. His priority on God shows the use of attitude marker, where God is showed as the supreme being that needs total

dedication, and who in turns blesses the affairs of those who are dedicated to him. In conclusion, all the modal verbs in the above excerpts were used as boosters to show the certainty in the proposition that Bishop Adhlakun hold that dedication is evident in one's work with God. So, through the various tools available in Hyland's (2005) Stance and Engagement Theory, Bishop Adhlakun has taken his stance that dedication can only be observed in one who works with God

Conclusion

It has been established in the literature that stance deals with judgement people have over certain issues. This study revealed that the message of Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun is imbued with his stances on the relevance of dedication to the Christian living. These stances include dedication is the only way to distinction, most Christians are not living dedicated purposeful life, the only ways to be dedicated are through focus and concentration and total dedication is evident in one's work with God. All the nine engagement markers (hedges, boosters, attitude markers, self-mention, reader/listener pronouns, directives, questions, shared knowledge and personal asides) were used by Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun. This study has implications on the study of religious discourse, besides its contributions to works on Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun. The study concludes that Bishop Taiwo Victor Adhlakun speeches on the "The Power of dedication" is imbued with various stances. The study also recommends that research should be conducted on the pragmatic acts in the message.

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